

Liste der Codes

Liste der Codes	Memo	Häufigkeit
Codesystem		49
Effects of the alliance on the university in the past		0
the alliance helped to sharpen the universities vision of impact orientation		1
The idea of the university as socially transforming unites the alliance partners	This idea was implicitly there but it was made explicit only through the alliance	3
Autonomy		0
No danger for autonomy because of alliance membership		1
The BA-MA system has been accepted		1
Most important changes	Transformation 1 - FQuestion 1	0
Challenge of trans- and interdisciplinarity because of mission-orientation		1
Due to pandemic acceleartion of digitalisation		1
quantiative increase in course offers and budget	This is due to a specific local problem of a double cohort of Abitur	1
alignment of studies and degrees of UAS and traditional universities		1
Bologna reform		1
university freedom, autonomy		3
Success of dealing with changes	Subaspect of changes	0
Some dualisms between UAS and traditional universities still exist		1

Digitalization and AI is still a challenge		1
technical management of autonomy is completed		3
not completed as for the budget management		1
Factors leading to change	Subquestion of changes	0
Third mission	One of the main changes in literature is the so called third mission.	0
Third mission is in the DNA of UAS		2
Interest groups	Transformation 1 - question 2	0
Changes regarding staff	Transformation 2 - question 3	0
personal development strategy orients itself on the third mission		1
Challenges regarding the participation in the alliance	Transformation 3 - question 4	0
Top-down is limited to the message, action must come bottom-up		1
Aligning strategic processes: with what rigour		1
More evolutionary bottom-up than killing top-down processes		2
not creating weaknesses but natural strength without pushing		1
Rely on the organic process for integration		1
emphasize the diversity of the institutions and ecosystems instead of mainstreaming		1
huge promises, little money		2
conflict of interest between original trust and utilitarianism		4

How to solve the conflict of interest?		4
Focus on topics has helped to realise the mission-oriented research strategy		1
Only focussing on solving mission related problems will not work		1
Legitimacy for society and expectations of universities advancing great missions		1
Effects of the alliance in 6-10 years	Trranformation 3 - question 5	0
university as a European player		1
Research beyond boundaries		1
Easy access and 50% student mobility		1
EU partners as standard portfolio of universities		1
Added value of the alliance	Transformation 3 - question 6	0
Anchoring of European Values		1
Priorisation of partnerships		1
Paraphrasierte Segmente		1